

ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE COMPLIANCE OF WINDOW UNITS WITH EXR1-EXR2 CLASSES BASED ON FIELD BLAST TEST RESULTS**Orlenko M.***Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture,
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ORCID: 0009-0001-9890-4520***Abstract**

The article analyses structural factors affecting the compliance of window units with EXR1-EXR2 blast-resistance classes based on full-scale field blast tests. The study is based on an experimental programme involving eleven window specimens of different compositions. Methodologically, the study distinguishes between an exploratory full-scale stage, during which critical structural zones were identified and technical hypotheses were verified, and a qualification stage, during which selected window systems were tested with official test protocols. It is shown that compliance with EXR classes is determined not by a single structural parameter, but by the systemic interaction of the insulating glass unit, the internal laminated pane, the frame profile, fittings, the fixed or floating mullion (stulp), and the installation joint. The use of shatter-resistant film and ESG tempered glass is considered separately. It was established that a film applied to glass without proper retention of the glazing within the frame cannot be regarded as an independent blast-protection solution and, under certain conditions, may form a large glass-film fragment hazardous to occupants. The experimental results also did not confirm the expected advantages of ESG in the tested insulating glass units compared with float glass. The key element of the insulating glass unit for reducing the risk of secondary fragments was identified as the internal 44.4 VSG laminated glass of P4A class. It is substantiated that the most extensively investigated configuration is the 'opening sash + fixed part' configuration separated by a fixed mullion, whereas floating-mullion (stulp) systems require further repeated testing.

Keywords: glazed building envelope elements, window units, shock wave, blast resistance, field blast tests, EXR1, EXR2, P4A, laminated glass, shatter-resistant film, tempered glass, fixed mullion, floating mullion (stulp).

Problem statement

Glazed building envelope elements are among the most vulnerable components of a building envelope under blast loading. Failure of the glass, frame profile, fittings or installation joint may lead not only to the loss of the enclosing function, but also to the formation of secondary fragments that are hazardous to occupants. According to the UNDSS information bulletin 'Blast Protection for Windows', in major bombing incidents 80% of victims were killed or injured by primary and secondary fragmentation, while flying glass fragments accounted for 80% of injuries and deaths caused by fragmentation [8]. This confirms that window systems should be considered not merely as enclosing elements, but also as potential sources of secondary injury.

The specific hazard associated with glazing is that, under blast overpressure, glass fragments may acquire velocity and kinetic energy sufficient to penetrate soft and hard surfaces [8]. Therefore, the objective of blast-resistant window design is not limited to preventing glass fracture; it also includes controlling the trajectory, size, mass and retention mechanism of fragments. In this context, strengthening a single component of the system does not guarantee safety: the glass, frame, fittings, anchorage and supporting substrate must be coordinated according to the principle of balanced protection.

For Ukrainian construction practice, the problem is particularly relevant because of damage to civil and critical infrastructure caused by blast effects. A common misconception is to equate the impact resistance of a separate material with the ability of the entire window unit to comply with an EXR class. In particular, the use of tempered glass or an applied shatter-resistant

film is often perceived as a sufficient protective measure. The full-scale tests performed in this study showed that such solutions must be evaluated only as part of a complete system, taking into account the method of glazing retention in the frame, the window configuration, the behaviour of the fixed or floating mullion (stulp), the installation joint and the actual shock-wave parameters.

Review of recent studies and publications

International practice for assessing the blast resistance of glazed structures is based on full-scale field tests, shock-tube tests, engineering calculations and numerical simulation. Test and classification criteria are reflected in EN 13123-2, EN 13124-2, EN 13541, ISO 16933, ASTM F1642 and GSA-TS01 [1-3; 5-7], whereas EN 356 is used to classify security glazing by resistance to manual attack and is relevant for characterising P4A class [4]. In these documents, not only the fact of glass fracture is important, but also the nature of fragment penetration into the protected space. Reviews of contemporary design methods for blast-resistant facades and windows emphasise the need to consider the glazed structure as a single system comprising the glazing, frame, fixings and supporting substrate [9; 17].

The UNDSS bulletin emphasises that the analysis of blast effects on windows should include the entire window system: glass, frame, anchorage, supporting substrate, glass type, threat parameters, standoff distance and angle of incidence of the blast wave [8]. It also notes that shatter-resistant film (SRF) can reduce fragment projection only when properly installed. The simplest 'daylight application' scheme, where the film is applied only within the visible glass area and is not captured by the frame, has only negligible effectiveness

for blast protection, whereas attached or mechanically anchored systems are substantially more effective [8].

The issue of laminated glass and its impact-resistance classes is regulated by EN 356. Class P4A belongs to the P1A-P5A group of impact-resistant security glazing and requires testing with a 4.11 kg steel ball dropped from a height of 9000 mm, with three impacts arranged in a triangle [4; 10]. At the same time, P4A is not a blast-resistance class; its relevance for the structures considered in this study lies in the ability of the laminated layer to retain glass fragments and reduce the risk of secondary injury.

Previous works by the author and co-authors considered international standards for testing glazed structures and summarised the experience of a series of full-scale field tests of eleven window-unit specimens [11; 12]. However, for further use of these results in the dissertation research, a separate analysis of the structural factors affecting compliance with EXR1-EXR2 classes is required, taking into account both the exploratory and qualification stages of the experimental programme.

Aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the article is to analyse structural factors affecting the compliance of window units with EXR1-EXR2 classes based on full-scale field blast tests, while scientifically distinguishing between the exploratory stage of full-scale experiments and the qualification stage of protocol-based tests.

To achieve this aim, the following tasks were addressed: the eleven tested specimens were systematised according to glazing composition, frame profile, fittings, configuration and method of result documentation; the specimens whose results were confirmed by official protocols were identified; the role of P4A laminated glass, shatter-resistant films and ESG tempered glass was clarified; the limits of transferring the results to similar types of structures were determined; and practical conclusions for further design and testing were formulated.

Materials and methods

The object of the study is window units of different compositions tested on an open field test range under the action of an air-blast shock wave. Within the experimental programme, eleven specimens were tested. They differed in the composition of insulating glass units, the material and type of frame profiles, fittings, additional reinforcements, structural configuration and installation joint [12].

For correct scientific interpretation, the results were divided into two functional levels. The first level consisted of exploratory full-scale experiments. Their purpose was to identify critical structural zones, verify technical hypotheses, compare basic and experimental solutions, and prepare constructions for subsequent qualification testing. Some specimens of this stage did not have a separate official protocol; nevertheless, their results are significant as engineering-research data.

The second level consisted of qualification field tests performed after analysing the results of the exploratory stage. At this stage, selected or structurally refined specimens were submitted for testing with official protocols. These protocols constitute the basis for conclusions regarding compliance or non-compliance with a specific EXR class [13-15].

The assessment was carried out in accordance with DSTU EN 13123-2:2006 and the procedural part of DSTU EN 13124-2:2006. The key criteria were: absence of through-holes or gaps through which a rigid 10 mm diameter rod can pass; prevention of hazardous fragment projection into the protected space; retention of frame, glass and metal components within the structure; and absence of component ejection from the rear side of the specimen [1; 2; 13-15].

Considering the limited number of specimens and the uneven variation of factors, a full predictive regression model was not applied. The results are presented as a practical factor analysis suitable for engineering generalisation, development of structural recommendations and planning of subsequent controlled tests.

Table 1.

Generalised matrix of eleven tested specimens

No.	Code / specimen	Stage	Profile	Glazing / IGU (summary)	Configuration	Result / documentation
1	S1-01_2022	exploratory	VEKA MD, PVC 82 mm	4-4-44.4 VSG (P4A)	1 sash + 1 fixed part, fixed mullion	EXR1 compliance according to exploratory-stage data; no separate protocol was issued
2	S1-02_2022	exploratory	VEKA MD, PVC 82 mm	6 ESG-4-44.4 VSG (P4A)	1 sash + 1 fixed part, fixed mullion	non-compliance with EXR2 according to exploratory-stage data; ESG did not provide the expected advantage
3	S2-01_2023	exploratory	EPSILON MD, PVC 70 mm	4-4-4 without VSG	1 sash + 1 fixed part, fixed mullion	structural failure; no separate protocol was issued
4	231 / S2-02_2023	qualification	VEKA MD, PVC 82 mm	4-4-44.4 VSG (P4A)	1 sash + 1 fixed part, fixed mullion	complies with EXR1 (NS); Protocol No. 4317/2023
5	345-B/1 / S3-01_2023	qualification	Reynaers ML8 HI, aluminium 77 mm	6-6-44.4 VSG (P4A)	1 sash + 1 fixed part, fixed mullion	complies with EXR2 (NS); Protocol No. 345-B/2023
6	345-B/2 / S3-02_2023	qualification	Reynaers Sunrise, aluminium 77 mm	6-6-44.4 VSG (P4A)	1 sash + 1 fixed part, fixed mullion	complies with EXR2 (NS); Protocol No. 345-B/2023
7	345-B/3 / S3-03_2023	qualification	VEKA MD, PVC 82 mm	4-4-44.4 VSG (P4A)	1 sash + 1 fixed part, fixed mullion	does not comply with EXR2 (NS); Protocol No. 345-B/2023
8	S4-01_2024	exploratory	EPSILON MD, PVC 70 mm	4-4 + applied shatter-resistant film	1 sash + 1 fixed part, fixed mullion	failure; film-retained glazing formed a large fragment; no separate protocol was issued
9	796-B/1 / S4-02_2024	qualification	Reynaers Sunrise, aluminium 77 mm	6-6-44.4 VSG (P4A)	double-sash	does not comply with EXR2 (NS); Protocol No. 796-B/2024
10	796-B/2 / S4-03_2024	qualification	VEKA MD, PVC 82 mm + aluminium cover	4-4-44.4 VSG (P4A)	1 sash + 1 fixed part, fixed mullion	complies with EXR2 (NS); Protocol No. 796-B/2024
11	796-B/3 / S4-04_2024	qualification	Reynaers Sunrise, aluminium 77 mm	6-6-44.4 VSG (P4A)	double-sash with floating mullion (stulp)	complies with EXR1 (NS); Protocol No. 796-B/2024

Note: the exploratory stage is considered as a full-scale experiment for identifying engineering regularities; the qualification stage is considered as testing with an official protocol and a determination of compliance or non-compliance with a specific EXR class.

Results and discussion

The systematisation of the eleven specimens shows that the experimental programme was broader than the set of specimens for which separate official protocols were issued. Such a structure is methodologically justified for applied research: at the first stage, full-scale experiments are conducted to identify critical zones and technical limitations, whereas at the second stage the refined structural solutions undergo qualification testing. Therefore, all eleven specimens were used

to analyse structural regularities, while conclusions regarding confirmation of EXR classes were formulated only for protocol-documented results.

The results recorded in official protocols allow the following relationships to be established: specimen 231 complied with EXR1 (NS); specimens 345-B/1 and 345-B/2 complied with EXR2 (NS); specimen 345-B/3 did not comply with EXR2 (NS); specimen 796-B/1 did not comply with EXR2 (NS); specimen 796-B/2 complied with EXR2 (NS); and specimen 796-B/3 complied with EXR1 (NS), not EXR2 (NS).

Specimens with official protocol documentation of results

Specimen	Protocol	Dis- tance, m	Pso, kPa	Pr, kPa	Class conclu- sion	Engineering interpretation of the result
231	No. 4317/2023	5	86*	228*	complies with EXR1 (NS)	PVC 82 mm + internal P4A laminated glass provided EXR1
345-B/1	No. 345-B/2023	3	576.3	826.0	complies with EXR2 (NS)	aluminium profile + 6 mm outer panes + P4A provided EXR2
345-B/2	No. 345-B/2023	3	415.5	892.5	complies with EXR2 (NS)	Reynaers Sunrise aluminium system confirmed EXR2
345-B/3	No. 345-B/2023	3	564.6	802.1	does not comply with EXR2 (NS)	PVC 82 mm without additional reinforcement did not provide EXR2
796-B/1	No. 796-B/2024	3	324.0	1013.1	does not comply with EXR2 (NS)	6 mm panes did not compensate for configuration and joint-related features
796-B/2	No. 796-B/2024	3	302.9	1117.2	complies with EXR2 (NS)	PVC + aluminium cover increased contour stiffness
796-B/3	No. 796-B/2024	5	86*	228*	complies with EXR1 (NS)	floating-mullion (stulp) aluminium system confirmed EXR1; one specimen is insufficient for generalisation

Note: values marked with "*" are given as calculated or reference values for the relevant load scenario; these values use the parameters adopted for EN 13123-2 classes and are consistent with the Kingery-Bulmash calculation approach [1; 16]. Pso is the incident overpressure; Pr is the reflected overpressure.

Analysis of structural factors affecting compliance with EXR1-EXR2 classes

Insulating glass unit composition and the role of the internal laminated pane. The test results indicate that the key element of the insulating glass unit is not merely the use of a thicker or tempered outer pane, but the presence of an internal laminated pane capable of retaining fragments after the first layers have failed. In most protocol-confirmed structures, after detonation the first two panes of the insulating glass unit fractured, whereas the internal 44.4 VSG laminated layer with four 0.38 mm interlayers cracked but did not allow through-failure or spalling from the rear side. This behaviour made it possible to meet the EXR criteria regarding the absence of fragments in the protected space.

P4A class should be considered as a characteristic of impact-resistant laminated glass according to EN 356, not as an independent blast-resistance class. Its practical significance for the tested structures is that the laminated pane, positioned as the third pane, i.e. the internal pane on the room side, acts as a barrier against fragments from the first and second panes of the insulating glass unit. Therefore, for blast-protective insulating glass units, the most appropriate arrangement is to place the P4A laminated glass on the internal side, where it acts as the final fragment-retention layer.

ESG tempered glass. The exploratory full-scale stage made it possible to verify the common assumption that tempered glass automatically increases the blast resistance of an insulating glass unit. The results of specimen S1-02_2022 did not confirm this assumption for the tested configuration: ESG fragmented into small pieces and, in terms of its behaviour under blast loading, did not provide a fundamental advantage compared with 6 mm float glass. Therefore, the advantages of ESG under static or impact loads cannot be directly

transferred to a short-duration blast impulse without full-scale verification of the specific system.

Shatter-resistant film. The result of specimen S4-01_2024 showed that applying a shatter-resistant film to glass without ensuring reliable retention of the glazing in the frame cannot be considered an independent blast-protection solution. Unlike failure with a dispersed cloud of small fragments, the film may bind glass fragments into a larger glass-film element in terms of mass and area; if ejected into the protected space, such an element produces a concentrated injury effect. This result is consistent with UNDSS recommendations, which state that the effectiveness of SRF depends on the installation method and that a daylight application without capture or anchorage in the frame has only negligible effectiveness for blast protection [8].

Frame profile system and stiffness of the load-bearing contour. Specimens 345-B/1 and 345-B/2 confirmed that aluminium profile systems have high potential for providing EXR2 in the 'opening sash + fixed part' configuration with a fixed mullion. At the same time, the result of specimen 796-B/1 showed that even an aluminium profile and 6 mm outer panes do not guarantee EXR2 if the configuration and joints of the structure create other critical load-transfer paths. Specimen 796-B/2 demonstrated the promise of a combined PVC + aluminium cover solution: with a 43.52 mm insulating glass unit and 4 mm outer panes, the structure complied with EXR2 owing to increased contour stiffness and the presence of internal P4A glazing.

Window-unit configuration. The most thoroughly tested configuration within the experimental programme was a two-part window unit separated by a fixed mullion: one fixed part and one opening sash.

This configuration provided the largest number of comparable results involving different insulating glass units, profiles and fittings. Therefore, the principal conclusions of the article primarily apply to this type of structure.

The floating-mullion (stulp) configuration was tested only on one specimen, 796-B/3, and confirmed compliance with EXR1. However, a single result is insufficient for scientifically justified generalisation regarding floating-mullion (stulp) systems. For this type of construction, a separate series of tests is required with repeated specimens and variation of the profile, locking scheme, number of locking points and load class.

Transferability of results. The results obtained for the 'opening sash + fixed part' configuration with a fixed mullion may be used as an engineering basis for single-sash and fixed windows, provided that the overall dimensions are similar or less critical, and that the

same insulating glass unit, profile system, fittings and installation joint are used. Such transfer is justified because fixed and single-sash constructions have a simpler load-bearing scheme and fewer potentially weak joints. At the same time, any increase in glazing area or change in profile, installation method or load class requires additional verification.

Fittings and installation joint. The use of RC2-class fittings is an important prerequisite for retaining the sash, but it cannot be regarded as an independent guarantee of blast resistance. Fittings are effective only in interaction with the profile, reinforcement, sash geometry, number of locking points and quality of the installation joint. The installation joint and fixings act as components of the load-bearing contour through which dynamic load is transferred to the supporting substrate. Therefore, for blast-resistant windows, installation must be designed as part of the protective system rather than as an auxiliary construction operation.

Table 3.

Practical significance of the main structural factors

Factor	Established significance	Limitation or risk	Practical conclusion
Internal 44.4 VSG laminated glass (P4A)	retains fragments from the first glass layers and reduces the risk of secondary injury	does not compensate for a weak frame, fittings or installation	should be used as the third, internal pane of the insulating glass unit
Shatter-resistant film	may hold small fragments together	without anchorage in the frame, it may form a large glass-film fragment	should not be regarded as an independent blast-protection solution without testing the specific system
ESG	has advantages under ordinary impact or service conditions	under the tested blast conditions it did not show a significant advantage over 6 mm float glass	should not be used as the main blast-protection criterion
Aluminium profile	increases the stiffness of the load-bearing contour	the result depends on configuration and joints	promising for EXR2, but requires system-level verification
PVC + aluminium cover	reinforces the profile contour and may provide EXR2	requires verification of the specific size and configuration	promising combined solution
Fixed-mullion scheme 'sash + fixed part'	the most extensively investigated configuration in the programme	results should not be automatically transferred to floating-mullion (stulp) systems	may serve as a basis for designing fixed and single-sash windows
Floating-mullion scheme	EXR1 was confirmed on one specimen	one test is insufficient for generalisation	requires a separate series of studies

Practical recommendations

For structures aimed at EXR1, it is advisable to use internal laminated glass of P4A class, a reinforced PVC profile of sufficient installation depth, fittings with an adequate number of locking points and an installation joint that transfers dynamic load to the supporting substrate. The result of specimen 231 confirms the viability of this concept for EXR1 under the corresponding load conditions.

For structures aimed at EXR2, aluminium profile systems or combined PVC + aluminium reinforcement solutions are more substantiated. The experience of specimens 345-B/1, 345-B/2 and 796-B/2 shows that compliance with EXR2 is formed not only by the insulating glass composition, but also by contour stiffness,

fittings performance, window-unit configuration and reliability of the installation joint.

It is not recommended to position ESG tempered glass or an applied shatter-resistant film as independent solutions for achieving blast resistance. ESG did not confirm the expected advantage under the tested conditions, while a shatter-resistant film without structural retention in the frame may change the failure pattern towards the formation of larger and heavier fragments. Such solutions may be used only as auxiliary elements after testing as part of the complete window system.

For floating-mullion (stulp) and double-sash systems, further research is required because their load-bearing scheme differs from the fixed-mullion configuration. Particular attention should be paid to the behaviour of the active and passive sashes, the number of

locking points, the stiffness of the central rebate and the behaviour of the installation joint under reflected pressure.

Conclusions

1. Within the experimental programme, eleven window specimens of different compositions were tested. Some specimens belonged to the exploratory full-scale stage without a separate official protocol, while others belonged to the qualification stage with protocol-based documentation of results.

2. The division of the programme into exploratory and qualification stages is methodologically justified: exploratory specimens make it possible to identify structural regularities, whereas claims regarding confirmation of an EXR class should be formulated only for results recorded in official protocols.

3. The key element of the insulating glass unit for reducing the risk of secondary fragments is the internal 44.4 VSG laminated glass of P4A class. In the tested structures, it acts as the third, internal pane retaining fragments from the first glass layers after their failure.

4. The exploratory full-scale experiments refuted the assumption that ESG tempered glass by itself provides a substantial advantage under blast loading. Under the tested conditions, its behaviour was close to that of float glass, and fragmentation did not guarantee the safety of the protected space.

5. Applying a shatter-resistant film without reliable retention of the glazing in the frame did not confirm its effectiveness as an independent blast-protection method. In specimen S4-01_2024, this scheme led to the formation of a large glass-film fragment, which may create a more concentrated injury effect than a dispersed cloud of small fragments.

6. The most thoroughly investigated configuration was the 'one opening sash + one fixed part' configuration separated by a fixed mullion. The results for this scheme may be used as an engineering basis for fixed and single-sash windows, provided that the dimensions are similar or less critical and the structural parameters remain unchanged.

7. The floating-mullion (stulp) configuration confirmed EXR1 on only one specimen; therefore, conclusions regarding floating-mullion (stulp) systems are preliminary and require continued full-scale testing.

8. Further studies should be conducted as a controlled factor experiment with sequential variation of one parameter at a time: glazing type, profile, opening configuration, fittings and installation joint.

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